

Chemistry of Aminobenzothiazoles: Oxidation of 1,5-Diaryl-2-*S*-ethyl-4-thiobiurets. *N*-2-Benzothiazolyl-*N'*-aryl-*S*-ethylisothiocarbamides and Related Guanidines

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Oxidation of 1,5-diaryl-2-*S*-ethyl-4-thiobiurets has been found to yield the related *N*-2-benzothiazolyl-*N'*-aryl-*S*-ethylisothiocarbamides and not the expected 1,2,4-thiadiazoles. Intraction of ammonia and the above isothiocarbamides affords the corresponding guanidines. The relevant structures have been confirmed by alternative synthesis.

Oxidation of *N*-aryl-substituted thiocarbamides leads to the formation of heterocyclic bases (Hector, *Ber.*, 1889, **22**, 1176). The chemistry of the one derived from *N*-phenylthiocarbamide has been recently reviewed (Suresh, *J. Sci. Res., B.H.U.*, 1958-59, **9**, 94; Ph.D. Thesis, B.H.U.); its isomeric transformation to 3,5-diphenylimino-1,2,4-thiadiazolidine (II), observed by Dost (*Ber.*, 1906, **39**, 863) and Kurzer (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1956, 2345; *Chem. Ind.*, 1956, 526), strongly suggests structure (I) for this substance.

Since 1,2,4-thiadiazoles are known to be formed (Kurzer *et al.*, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1955, 1, 2288; 1956, 2345, 4524; 1957, 2999) by oxidative cyclisation of compounds, which include the system -C(:NH)-NH-C(:S)-, it appears likely, although Kurzer and Taylor (*ibid.*, 1958, 379) have opined otherwise, that 1,5-diaryl-2-*S*-ethyl-4-thiobiurets (III) is oxidised thus:

Replacement of an S.Et group in (IV) by an :NH group furnishes (I), the expected structure of Hector's base.

Several compounds of type (III) (where Ar = phenyl, *o*-, *m*-, and *p*-tolyl, and α -naphthyl) were prepared and oxidised under a variety of conditions to the corresponding oxidation products, which on treatment with ethanolic ammonia in a sealed tube replaced their -S.Et group with :NH, affording derivatives isomeric with Hector's bases. These amido and *S*-ethyl derivatives were identified with the appropriate *N*-2-benzothiazolyl-*N'*-arylguanidines (VI) and *N*-2-benzothiazolyl-*N'*-aryl-*S*-ethylisothiocarbamides (V). The sequence of these changes can be represented as:

Compounds (V) and (VI) have been prepared also by an alternative route: from the related *N*-2-benzothiazolyl-*N'*-arylthiocarbamides (Joshua, this *Journal*, 1960, **37**, 621; vide Experimental).

The expected 1, 2, 4-thiadiazole derivatives were not obtained.

EXPERIMENTAL

1,5-Diaryl-2-*S*-ethyl-4-thiobiurets were readily obtained by condensing the appropriate *N*-aryl-*S*-ethylisothiocarbamide with the desired aryl isothiocyanate. A typical set of details leading to the formation of 1,5-diphenyl-2-*S*-ethyl-4-thiobiuret is given below.

Phenylthiocarbamide (15 g.) was refluxed on a water bath with ethyl iodide (8.5 c.c.) in ethanol (25 c.c.). The *S*-ethyl-*N*-phenylisothiuronium iodide obtained was basified; the free base was extracted with benzene (Bertram, *Ber.*, 1892, **25**, 55). The benzene extract after drying over calcium chloride was treated with the requisite quantity (13.5 c.c.) of phenyl isothiocyanate. After warming on a water bath for 1 to 2 hours the expected isodithiobiuret was formed (16 g.). It was crystallised from solvents, such as, ethanol, ethyl acetate, or methanol. The other diaryl-isodithiobiurets were prepared similarly. Physical characteristics and analytical data of the respective diarylisodithiobiurets are shown in Table I.

TABLE I

No.	Reactants.	Diaryl-2- <i>S</i> -ethyl-4-thiobiuret.	M.P.	Cryst. from	Formula.	Found.	Calc.
* 1.	<i>S</i> -Ethylphenyl-T + phenyl I	1,5-Diphenyl-	93°	EtOH	C ₁₆ H ₁₇ N ₃ S ₂	N:13.40%	13.33%
2.	<i>S</i> -Ethyl- <i>o</i> -tolyl-T + <i>o</i> -tolyl I	1,5-Di- <i>o</i> -tolyl-	87°	EtAc	C ₁₈ H ₂₁ N ₃ S ₂	C:63.06 H: 6.16 N:12.28	62.97 6.12 12.24
3.	<i>S</i> -Ethyl- <i>m</i> -tolyl-T + <i>m</i> -tolyl I	1,5-Di- <i>m</i> -tolyl-	72°	EtOH	..	C:62.81 H: 5.98 N:11.99	62.97 6.12 12.24
4.	<i>S</i> -Ethyl- <i>p</i> -tolyl-T + <i>p</i> -tolyl I	1,5-Di- <i>p</i> -tolyl-	112°	EtOH	..	C:63.01 H: 6.14 N:12.06	62.97 6.12 12.24
5.	<i>S</i> -Ethyl- <i>α</i> -naphthyl-T + <i>α</i> -naphthyl I	1,5-Di- <i>α</i> -naphthyl	135°	Benzene	C ₂₄ H ₂₁ N ₃ S ₂	N: 9.80	10.06

N.B. T and I represent respectively isothiocarbamide and isothiocyanate.

* Johnson and Crammer, *Am. Chem. J.*, 1903, **30**, 81.

Oxidation of 1,5-Diaryl-2-*S*-ethyl-4-thiobiuret

(a) *With Bromine in Ethanol.*—To a clear solution of 1,5-diaryl-2-*S*-ethyl-4-thiobiuret (0.02*M*) in ethanol (30 c.c.), acidified with HBr (2 c.c.), was added a solution of bromine (1.1 c.c., 0.02*M*) in dilute ethanol with efficient stirring. The colour of bromine was gradually discharged with the separation of the hydrobromide of the base as a colorless crystalline solid. It was crystallised from boiling ethanol. The five diarylisodithiobiurets were oxidised in a similar manner.

Oxidation of the diarylisodithiobiurets with bromine in benzene or chloroform medium was also found to afford the same products as obtained above in an ethanolic medium. Physical characteristics and analytical data of the respective oxidation products are shown in Table II.

(b) *With Iodine in Ethanol.*—To a clear ethanolic solution of the diarylisodithiobiuret was added iodine in ethanol with stirring till the iodine colour was discharged. The hydroiodide precipitated was filtered, washed with ethanol, and dried. The hydroiodides obtained by the oxidation of the four diarylisodithiobiurets melted respectively at 132°, 140°, 142° and 138°

(as shown in order in Table I). The free bases obtained from these hydroiodides had the same m.p.'s as the bases obtained from the above hydrobromides.

TABLE II
N-2-Benzothiazolyl-N'-phenyl-S-ethylisothiocarbamides.

No.	Diaryl-2-S-ethyl-4-thiobiuret oxidised.	Oxidation product.	M.P.	Hydrobromide, Equiv.		Free base. M.P. Formula.	Found.	Calc.
				Found.	Calc.			
1.	1,5-Diphenyl-	N-2-B-N'-phenyl-S (C ₁₆ H ₁₂ N ₂ S ₂ , HBr)*	198°	401.4	398	83° C ₁₆ H ₁₂ N ₂ S ₂	C:60.81% H: 4.69 N:13.30	61.34% 4.79 13.41
2.	1,5-Di- <i>o</i> -tolyl-	N-2-(4-Methyl)-B-N'- <i>o</i> -tolyl-S (C ₁₄ H ₁₀ N ₂ S ₂ , HBr)	185°	422.7	422	67° C ₁₄ H ₁₀ N ₂ S ₂	C:62.87 H: 5.49 N:12.28	63.34 5.55 12.31
3.	1,5-Di- <i>m</i> -tolyl-	N-2-(5-Methyl)-B-N'- <i>m</i> -tolyl-S (C ₁₄ H ₁₀ N ₂ S ₂ , HBr)	162°	423.2	422	97° ..	C:62.97 H: 5.72 N:11.99	63.34 5.55 12.31
4.	1,5-Di- <i>p</i> -tolyl-	N-2-(6-Methyl)-B-N'- <i>p</i> -tolyl-S (C ₁₄ H ₁₀ N ₂ S ₂ , HBr)	184°	424.7	422	99° ..	C:63.54 H: 5.72 N:12.10	63.34 5.55 12.31
5.	1,5-Di- <i>α</i> -naphthyl-	N-2- <i>α</i> -Naphthiazolyl-N'- <i>α</i> -naphthyl-S (C ₂₄ H ₁₆ N ₂ S ₂ , HBr)	168°	500.2	499	176° C ₂₄ H ₁₆ N ₂ S ₂	N: 9.98	10.16

S and B represent respectively S-ethylisothiocarbamide hydrobromide and benzothiazolyl.

Formation of N-2-Benzothiazolyl-N'-arylguanidines

N-2-Benzothiazolyl-N'-aryl-S-ethylisothiocarbamides (2 g.) and strong ethanolic ammonia (10 c.c.) were taken in a sealed tube and heated in a bomb furnace at 100-10° for about 4 to 6 hours. The contents of the sealed tube after breaking were boiled to remove excess of ammonia and ethyl mercaptan, formed in the reaction, and left for crystallisation. The crystals were collected and recrystallised from ethanol. Picrates and hydrochlorides of the bases were prepared. Melting points and analyses of the guanidines obtained are recorded in Table III.

TABLE III

No.	Amido derivatives.		M.P.	%Nitrogen.		Hydrochlorides.		Picrate m.p.
	S-Ethylisothiocarbamide.	Guanidine.		Found.	Calc.	M.P.	Formula.	
1.	N-2-B-N'-phenyl-S	N-2-B-N'-phenyl-G (C ₁₄ H ₁₂ N ₄ S)	154°	21.00%	20.90%	203-205°	C ₁₄ H ₁₂ N ₄ S.HCl	305.1 304.9 *227°
2.	N-2-(4-Methyl)-B-N'- <i>o</i> -tolyl-S	N-2-(4-Methyl)-B-N'- <i>o</i> -tolyl-G (C ₁₂ H ₁₀ N ₄ S)	170°	18.80	19.01	217°	C ₁₂ H ₁₀ N ₄ S.HCl	335.0 332.5 240°
3.	N-2-(5-Methyl)-B-N'- <i>m</i> -tolyl-S	N-2-(5-Methyl)-B-N'- <i>m</i> -tolyl-G (C ₁₂ H ₁₀ N ₄ S)	195°	18.40	19.01	196°	C ₁₂ H ₁₀ N ₄ S.HCl	331.0 332.5 192°
4.	N-2-(6-Methyl)-B-N'- <i>p</i> -tolyl-S	N-2-(6-Methyl)-B-N'- <i>p</i> -tolyl-G (C ₁₂ H ₁₀ N ₄ S)	198°	19.20	19.01	196°	C ₁₂ H ₁₀ N ₄ S.HCl	332.7 332.5 227°
	N-2- <i>α</i> -Naphthiazolyl-N'- <i>α</i> -naphthyl-S	N-2- <i>α</i> -Naphthiazolyl-N'- <i>α</i> -naphthyl-G (C ₂₂ H ₁₆ N ₄ S)	225°	15.31	15.21	245°	C ₂₂ H ₁₆ N ₄ S.HCl	410.2 404.5 272°

B, S, and G represent respectively benzothiazolyl, isothiocarbamide, and guanidine.

* Joshua, loc. cit.

The identity of (1)–(4) above was further confirmed by mixed m.p.'s with authentic samples (Joshua, *loc. cit.*), when no depression was recorded.

S-Ethyl-N-2-benzothiazolyl-N'-arylisothiocarbamides

N-2-Benzothiazolyl-N'-phenyl-, N-2-(4-methyl)-benzothiazolyl-N'-o-tolyl-, N-2-(5-methyl)-benzothiazolyl-N'-m-tolyl-, and N-2-(6-methyl)-benzothiazolyl-N'-p-tolyl-thiocarbamides were prepared (Joshua, *loc. cit.*). The required thiocarbamide (2 g.) was suspended in acetone-methanol mixture (1 : 1); 10% NaOH solution (5 c.c.) and ethyl iodide (1 c.c.) were added, and the mixture was heated for 3 to 4 hours on a water bath under reflux. The reaction mixture was filtered hot, basified with alkali, and kept aside for crystallisation. Crystals were collected and recrystallised from solvents like methanol, ethanol, and ethyl acetate.

(i). *N-2-Benzothiazolyl-N'-phenyl-S-ethylisothiocarbamide*: M.P. 83°. (Found: C, 60.81; H, 4.69; N, 13.3. $C_{16}H_{18}N_3S_2$ requires C, 61.34; H, 4.79; N, 13.41%). Mixed m.p. with the base obtained by the oxidation of 1,5-diphenyl 2-*S*-ethyl-4-thiobiuret remained undepressed.

(ii). *N-2-(4-Methyl)benzothiazolyl-N'-o-tolyl-S-ethylisothiocarbamide*: M. P. 67°. (Found: N, 12.2. $C_{16}H_{19}N_3S_2$ requires N, 12.31%). Its m.p. remained undepressed with the base obtained by oxidation of the corresponding isodithiobiuret.

(iii). *N-2-(5-Methyl)benzothiazolyl-N'-m-tolyl-S-ethylisothiocarbamide*: M. P. 93°; mixed m.p. with the base obtained by the oxidation of 1, 5-di-*m*-tolyl-2-*S*-ethyl-4-thiobiuret remained undepressed.

The *N-2-(6-methyl)benzothiazolyl-N'-p-tolyl-S-ethylisothiocarbamide* could not be obtained in a crystalline condition.

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